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THE IMPORTANCE OF DIVERSIFICATION OF EXPORT COMPOSITION IN ENSURING ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN THE REGION

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Annotation: This thesis analyzes the theoretical and practical aspects of diversification of export composition in ensuring regional economic development. The study highlights the main mechanisms of export diversification influencing regional economic growth, including the role of expanding the production structure, increasing value added, conquering new markets and ensuring economic stability. In addition, on the example of Uzbekistan and regions the current state of export structure is assessed, showing that it relies mainly on raw materials. As a result of the study, it is substantiated that export diversification is an important factor in increasing regional competitiveness, creating new jobs and ensuring sustainable economic development.

Keywords: export, diversification, regional development, competitiveness, export potential, economic growth

In the conditions of modern globalization, the provision of regional economic development is one of the priority areas of economic policy. The sustainable economic growth of the territories largely depends on their export potential and the effectiveness of their export structure. In particular, the diversification of the export composition – the expansion of the diversity of products and services – is manifested as an important factor of regional economic development.

According to official statistics, the total export volume of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2024 **approached 34 billion US dollars**, which is almost 1.5 times more than in 2019 (State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2024). At the same time, the share of raw materials and semi-finished products in exports is still high, which, according to some estimates, account for more **than 60% of total exports** (Mamatov B.Q., 2024).

Analysis by regions shows that despite the increase in export volumes, it is not sufficiently diversified structurally. For example, in the Khorezm region, the volume of exports increased **from USD 66.2 million in 2016 to USD 340 million in 2024**, which is a significant growth, but the main components of exports are dominated by textiles and agricultural products (author's calculation based on regional statistics).

There is also a positive trend in exports of services. In particular, the export of IT services reached the level of more **than \$ 100 million in 2020 and more than \$ 300 million in 2023**, which shows the growing role of the services sector in exports (IT Park Uzbekistan, 2023–2025).

It is also observed that employment indicators are directly related to exports. According to official data of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the share of employed population in export-oriented industries **has increased by 15-20%** in recent years (State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2024).

The impact of export diversification on economic development has been extensively investigated in scientific research. In particular, Albert O. Hirschman assesses diversification as a factor in economic stability, arguing that the narrow specialization of the composition of exports weakens the economic system to external shocks. He believes that the concentration of the composition of foreign trade will exacerbate economic risks.

A study by Imbs Jean and Romain Wacziarg substantiated that an increase in the level of diversification in the early stages of economic development accelerates economic growth. They explain diversification by the structural complexity of the economic system and the formation of new industries.

In addition, A. P. Petrov and A. M. Aronov assess diversification as a means of efficient use of resources and risk reduction.

Diversification of export composition has an impact on regional economic development through the following key mechanisms:

- expansion of the production structure and the formation of new industries;
- an increase in the share of high value-added products;
- increase in employment rates and incomes of the population;
- strengthening external economic stability;
- increased competitiveness of territory.

International experience shows that countries with diversified exports have higher economic growth rates, and according to some studies, the GDP growth rate is on average **1.5–2 times higher** in countries with an increased share of high-tech products (Imbs & Wacziarg, 2003).

The above analyses show that diversification of export composition is a strategic factor that has a comprehensive and multifaceted impact in ensuring regional economic development. First, it reduces the dependence of the region's economy on external factors and increases stability in relation to global market

fluctuations. Second, diversification serves to increase the share of high-value-added products by stimulating structural modernization of production.

Third, export diversification strengthens socio-economic stability by creating new jobs in the regions. Fourth, this process increases investment attractiveness and expands opportunities to attract foreign capital. Fifth, diversification will enhance the region's integration into global value chains and increase its international competitiveness.

In this context, it is necessary to implement at the regional level an integrated policy aimed at diversifying the export structure. In this direction, deepening of industry, introduction of innovative technologies, development of logistics infrastructure, support of export enterprises are of great importance. Strategies developed especially taking into account regional characteristics can yield effective results in ensuring regional economic development.

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